

The Role of Government in Promoting the Fourth Industrial Revolution: A View through the Lens of Empathy

N France and V Jarbandhan

School of Public Management, Governance and Public Policy, University of Johannesburg, South Africa

The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) brings a major shift that is changing economies, societies, and governance around the world. Governments play an essential role in steering this change as technology intersects with issues such as socio-economic inequality, unemployment, and limited institutional resources. This article argues that progressing the 4IR should not rely solely on technology and policy changes. It also requires a focus on governance that emphasises empathy and makes digital transformation more human. Using a qualitative and conceptual approach, the article examines how empathy can shape government strategies to encourage inclusive digital development, address the digital divide, and reduce the human impact of automation. The analysis indicates that empathy helps policymakers anticipate social effects, create people-focused policies, and build public trust in governance during this period of digital change. The article aims to explore how government can support the 4IR by showing how promoting empathy in policymaking, leadership, and governance can enable the government to effectively fulfil this crucial role in the South African public sector.

Keywords: Empathy, fourth industrial revolution, emotional intelligence, governance, human-centric leadership

The 4IR encompasses more than simply advancements in technology. It signifies a significant shift in how governments operate and connect with citizens in South Africa. Mkhize, Kayembe, and Thusi (2024:2) highlight that the public service recognises the importance of the 4IR and its ability to drive socio-economic growth. Layton-Matthews and Landsberg (2022:62) agree that the 4IR offers the public sector a valuable opportunity to boost socio-economic development. Since the public sector determines the government's policy direction, it is essential in developing the 4IR to reflect the values and goals of South Africa's public sector. Philbeck and Davis (2018) describe the 4IR as a time when digital technologies merge. These technologies serve as a catalyst for change in every aspect of work and daily life, fundamentally changing how economic, social, and political value is created, shared and exchanged. Kayembe and Nel (2019) back up this definition by stating that the 4IR marks the ongoing period of digital change. This change includes the merging of digitally connected products and services, as well as an increasing movement toward automation in homes and businesses.

The 4IR period is driven by advances in sectors such as genetics, nanotechnology, biotechnology, 3D printing, and the application of smart systems and supply chains (Schwab & Samans in the Future of Jobs Report, 2016). Thus, according to Mkhize et al. (2024:10), the 4IR is expected to make a huge impact on all sectors of people's lives.

It will alter the relationship between people and technology, as well as the effects of work, but with regard to focus, this study will concentrate on the government of South Africa. Governments are faced with pressures to transform their governance models, their relationship with their people, and their policy-making processes (World Economic Forum in Jarbandhan, 2017). Moreover, future successful public sectors in their approach to 4IR change will require their effectiveness in implementing 4IR-related technologies (Campbell, 2019:1).

The development of a nation heavily relies on the pivotal role played by governments. They determine how societies are going to react to changes that come with the 4IR. With the use of digital technology by many countries, questions have been raised concerning inclusiveness, ethics and human aspects of governance with relation to the 4IR. The 4IR simultaneously poses threats and opportunities for the South African government. On one hand, Li, Hou, and Wu (2017) observed that the 4IR provides a brighter future for economic development by enhancing productivity. In addition, it alters the global value chain. On the other hand, another threat of the 4IR is job displacement. Jobs that are less skilled in areas such as agriculture and production are under threat from robot technology that can perform these jobs faster and better (Caetano & Charamba, 2017). The significance of comprehending the function of empathy in these threats and opportunities arising from the 4IR for the South African government has been underscored above. The government should therefore not play a role in the promotion of the 4IR that is solely technological.

Author Note

N France, School of Public Management, Governance and Public Policy, University of Johannesburg, South Africa
V Jarbandhan, School of Public Management, Governance and Public Policy, University of Johannesburg, South Africa
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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to N France, School of Public Management, Governance and Public Policy, University of Johannesburg, South Africa
E-mail: nyamekofrance@gmail.com

Method

The study used a qualitative research approach, which is appropriate for the examination of the complicated, specific, and human-centric dimension of governance in the 4IR. In fact, the use of the qualitative research approach provides an in-depth explanation of the relationship, in social and motivational terms, between empathy and the policymaking and organisational culture dimensions of leadership in this aspect of the 4IR. According to Ahmed (2025), the

social sciences today rely heavily on the use of the qualitative research methodology.

In doing so, this study employed unobtrusive research methods because they enable the researcher to obtain information from already existing sources without coming into contact with research participants. This is considered objective with adequate interpretation. Auriacombe (2007:458) argues that such methods are particularly useful in cases where one wants to gather information without affecting either the natural setting or the participants' behaviours.

Documentary analysis of secondary sources was followed utilised and entails the examination of the policy documents, reports, and frameworks such as NDP 2030, PC4IR Report, and ICT Policy White Paper. This entailed an examination of the relevant literature with the intent of understanding the approach of the government in embracing the 4IR and its digital transformation initiatives. Content analysis entailed the examination of academic publications, journals, newspapers, and literature in the form of books written about the relationship between governance, empathy and the 4IR. The documents were chosen for their pertinence to the South African government's 4IR policy, other public sector governance frameworks, and empathy or emotional intelligence in organisational contexts. Sources included government white papers from 2016-2024, peer-reviewed articles from public administration and management journals, and official government strategy documents. Content analysis focused on explicit and implicit references to human-centric governance, workforce development and the ethical considerations in 4IR implementation.

The article relies on a literature review of studies conducted across public administration, management studies, ethics, and online governance. The strategy benefited the development of a well-rounded comprehension of the mechanisms through which governments may adopt a sense of empathy to promote inclusive and sustainable participation within the context of the 4IR. The qualitative strategy developed a foundation for conceptual analysis that resulted in interpretative arguments based on credible academic proof rather than numerical statistics. The strategy aligns with the article's objective of critically analysing the role of the public sector in promoting the 4IR from the perspective of empathy.

By conducting a detailed review of the existing literature on the subject matter, the article was able to incorporate ideas from across multiple disciplines such as public administration and management studies in an attempt to synthesise concepts and findings from this diversified range of sources and put together a well-rounded understanding on how the concept of empathy can be adopted as a basis for inclusive and sustainable involvement in the 4IR by the government. The unobtrusive method was therefore pivotal in ensuring that this could be achieved. The methodological approach aligns with the article's purpose of critically discussing the public sector's role in promoting the 4IR through an empathetic lens.

Understanding the 4IR In The Governance Context

Governments are both facilitators and regulators of the 4IR. Their main responsibilities include:

- Creating policy frameworks is essential. Policies like the National Integrated ICT Policy White Paper of 2016 aim to expand digital access and readiness. Manda and Backhouse (2017) explain that the white paper sets up a framework intended to drive the country

towards being more inclusive and innovative in terms of the approaches that are digitally driven. It describes the government's plan for leading 4IR efforts across all sectors while encouraging various stakeholders to join in advancing digital transformation (South African Government, 2016).

- The financial investments in digital infrastructure help both rural and urban communities to use broadband, smart systems, and e-Governance services. According to Fang (2002:1-22), e-Governance helps to promote citizen engagement via electronic systems such as e-democracy, internet voting systems, and other political activities on the internet. One major drawback to embracing the technology of the 4IR is that there is a disparity in digital infrastructure in urban and rural communities. Despite efforts to ensure rapid digital transformation in the country, e-services and e-governance are more established in urban areas (Oblaitan, Issah, & Wayi, 2021). Metropolitan municipalities may have internet connectivity and infrastructure to enable digitalisation, but many rural communities do not have internet connectivity and telecommunication infrastructure. Shibambu (2024:2) argues that the deficiency in digital infrastructure hinders the government's capacity to render digital government initiatives through digital platforms.
- Developing digital literacy by cultivating a workforce with digital skills, which will be crucial for the competitiveness of the 4IR. Such considerations involve the incorporation of coding, robotics, and AI into education structures. Van der Westhuizen (2021:97) examines the function of the government within the digital age and claims that the 4IR will change the economies and societies of the world in ways that have never been seen before. Thus, the public sector will have the task of ensuring that the workforce is aligned with the needs of the 4IR (Van der Westhuizen 2021:97). Hattig (2018:16) contends that if the necessary intervention is not provided by the public sector, the 4IR could lead to increased digital inequality in society and a skills gap in the workforce.
- Regulating technological ethics entails the government's role in safeguarding citizens against data exploitation, privacy violations, and algorithmic bias. According to Jarbandhan (2021), 4IR technologies create ethical dilemmas that the public sector often struggles to manage. Ethical problems related to automated decision-making and job displacement from the 4IR need careful regulation and intervention from the public sector.

These interventions and responsibilities highlight the important role of government in supporting the 4IR. It is crucial that they focus on empathy and keep human welfare at the centre of digital transformation in society.

Empathy as a Framework for Governance in the 4IR

Badea and Pana (2010:71) describe empathy as the capacity to grasp the emotions and feelings of other people. Jahoda (2005) further argues that empathy entails trying to step into someone else's shoes. This enhances the creation of mutual understanding and bonds between different individuals in different settings. Frankel (2017:55-56) highlights the significance of appreciating the role of empathy and emotional intelligence in our social interactions in the 4IR, characterised by fast growth in technology, towards building a respectable and coherent society in every aspect. Empathy and emotional intelligence are closely linked, as both focus on how we

respond to our own feelings while managing others' emotions. This includes understanding how one's perspective on a situation influences their feelings, as Badea and Pana (2010:71) point out. Goleman (1998) supports this by stating that emotional intelligence involves key aspects like self-awareness, motivation and empathy.

Empathy entails the capacity to understand and share the feelings and experiences of other people (Boyte, 2017). In this aspect, it provides a humanistic perspective when it comes to governance. The perspective enables policymakers to factor in the experience of citizens and government workers when implementing digital transformation and policies concerning the 4IR. In this context, policymakers put themselves in the position of citizens and public servants and ensure that the government achieves its service delivery mission. Furthermore, it is essential to consider that empathy is crucial for personal and societal relationships and processes. It helps people express and understand each other's experiences, needs and aspirations. This connection fosters positive interactions and cooperative behaviour (Riess, 2017:74-77). Positive associations and collective actions are crucial when it comes to the government because public servants have to develop good relations among themselves to enhance collective cultural values and efficiencies of the respective public institutions.

Mayer and Oosthuizen (2021) observed that public institutions often face rapid disruptions. The changes tend to trigger emotional responses among the government employees and the recipients of the services. Common feelings include anxiety and confusion, where some individuals in the public sector may have a hard time adjusting to the fast pace of change, which may result in substantial employment reductions within the public sector (Van der Westhuizen, 2021:91). In this setting, empathy-driven governance means the government recognises the worries of workers whose jobs might be at risk due to automation. It involves understanding the challenges faced by communities that do not have digital access and creating inclusive policies that focus on training, reskilling and fair opportunities. An empathetic government acknowledges that technological progress should not undermine social justice or human dignity. Instead, empathy serves as a moral guide that connects technological growth with the well-being of society.

Empathy and Capacity Building

According to Van der Westhuizen's (2021:97), analysis of the public sector's role in the digital age, the 4IR will drastically alter economies and societies. To meet the demands of the 4IR, the public sector must prioritise training its workforce (Van der Westhuizen 2021:97). This demonstrates how crucial the government and its leadership are in determining the course of the 4IR.

In South African government institutions, empathy is essential. Public employees must adapt to new digital workflows and tools. Uncertainty and fear of losing one's job are frequently brought on by this shift. The possibility of employment reductions as a result of 4IR features like automation, which is a major threat to employment, is a major concern (Sutherland, 2020:235). Jarbandhan (2021) claims that the 4IR has brought disruptive technologies that the public workforce finds challenging to adopt, causing employees who have trouble with new technology to feel confused and anxious. Five million jobs could potentially be lost globally as a result of the 4IR, according to Shave and Hofisi (2017:203). Therefore, leaders in government organisations must acknowledge these significant

issues and react with emotional intelligence. They ought to foster an emotionally uplifting atmosphere that unites, inspires, and motivates people. According to Holmes (2024), organisations can align their values with their objectives by adopting an empathetic leadership style that fosters collaboration and appropriate reactions to emotional situations. Additionally, Holmes (2024) points out that leaders who strongly emphasise empathy can develop a motivated and resilient workforce that can adjust to the uncertainties of the 4IR. These days, empathy fosters team resilience in trying times, emotional cohesion, and shared decision-making. Ultimately, empathy is not just a soft skill; it is a strategic asset that can help leaders engage with the human side of their roles, moving beyond merely managing tasks (Badea & Pana, 2010).

Through this lens, empathetic leadership entails being aware of the emotional difficulties associated with adjusting to new technology and providing the assistance required for public employees to thrive in settings that undergo constant change. Dassah (2014:361) asserts that the public sector must make large investments in educating public officials on how to take advantage of 4IR technologies in their work in order to handle the rapid changes of the 4IR. According to Manda and Backhouse (2017:1), better management of the effects of the 4IR is made possible by the government's capacity for digital preparation. To increase productivity, create value, and enhance social well-being, digital transformation entails integrating disruptive technologies (Ebert & Duarte, 2018).

The Ethical Imperative of Empathy in the 4IR

Nhede (2018:202) noted that the major changes created by the 4IR lead to a high degree of anxiety. Nhede, Mazenda, and Masiya (2022:5) further assert that preparing the public sector for the 4IR should emphasise the role of labour, recognise the public sector's contribution to society, and guarantee that job security remains a top national priority. There is growing concern that digitalisation could further marginalise the poor, unskilled workers, exacerbating already existing disparities, since the 4IR requires a skilled and flexible workforce (Schwab, 2016). Similarly, the increasing automation of routine tasks demonstrates that many tasks currently performed by human workers can be completed by machines (Susskind & Susskind, 2015). The public sector faces a challenge as a result.

Empathy can be cultivated in government institutions to address the ethical issues raised by the digital transformation. This ability can help policymakers foresee unforeseen consequences. Empathy enables people to take into account the opinions, emotions, and concerns of others (Badea & Pana, 2010). By taking this stance, public employees can consider the moral and ethical ramifications of the 4IR for both themselves and their nation's citizens. According to Jarbandhan (2021), public leaders frequently find it difficult to resolve the moral conundrums raised by 4IR technologies. In digital governance, an empathy-focused government prioritises social justice, accountability, and transparency. It calls on governments to enact laws that prevent exclusion of vulnerable populations while promoting moral innovations. Msila (2022:459) asserts that ethical behaviour is a quality that public employees cannot compromise. Accordingly, it is the state's duty to promote the 4IR through frameworks and policies motivated by empathy that also take into account the moral and ethical conundrums raised by the 4IR.

Challenges and Prospects of the 4IR in the South African Context

Adopting the 4IR presents structural and capability issues for the government. Transformation initiatives are still being hampered by a lack of infrastructure, the digital divide, financial problems, and opposition to change (Shibambu, 2024). Empathy can still be used to promote inclusive transformation, though. The government may make the digital revolution more human-centric by incorporating empathy into public engagement, leadership development, and policy formation. Empathetic governance principles that prioritise human empowerment and equitable digital advancement can be applied via programmes like the National e-Government Programme.

The 4IR is characterised by the blending of technologies that make it difficult to distinguish between the public and private sectors, as well as between the physical and digital worlds. This makes public sector governance a challenge (International Institute for Applied Systems (IIASA) 2020:14). It can spur innovation and enhance service delivery, but it also presents complicated problems, particularly in a developing nation like South Africa (Van der Westhuizen, 2021:85). These includes can be found in a variety of public sector governance domains, including infrastructural preparedness, institutional adaptability, human resources.

The Local Government Sector Education and Training Authority (2020) reported that most employees in local government do not possess the required skills to respond effectively to digital-era demands. This highlights a disconnect between the rapid advancement of technology and the public sector's capacity to adapt. This impedes innovation and causes inefficiencies in digital transition. This issue is exacerbated by the public sector's lack of targeted digital skill development, which leads to persistent underperformance and inequality (Hatting, 2018).

The government cannot effectively participate in or control the digital economy without efficient human resource development. Organisational and industrial psychologists emphasise the importance of helping workers develop their abilities and adapt to the 4IR (Ghislieri, Moline, & Cortese, 2018). Additionally, Singaram and Mayer (2022) contend that effective skill development in public organisations requires a robust and creative culture. While taking into account the larger societal context in which public organisations operate, this culture should support 4IR principles in both its leaders and employees.

The primary goal of government in the 4IR era, according to Chilunjika (2024:398), is to deliver high-quality services with minimal resources, saving time and money. AI and other 4IR technologies help public workers by streamlining decision-making procedures while the government tackles difficult issues (Chilunjika 2024:398). Advanced IT software and artificial intelligence (AI) can enhance data-driven processes that need substantial information gathering and processing on civilian affairs (Valle-Cruz, Contreras, & Munoz-Chaves, 2022). Nhede, Mazenda, and Masiya (2022:6) stated that since technology facilitates the availability and utilisation of reliable data, innovations such as automation are likely to enhance service delivery. As a result, coordination and information exchange across government agencies are made easier. Policymaking becomes more informed and inclusive when data is readily available, accessible and regularly shared throughout government agencies.

Van der Westhuizen (2021:94) reported that the 4IR gives governments the chance to store employee data on digital platforms. Public sector leaders will always have online access to personnel data due to this.

The 4IR, according to Richards (2019), provides public institutions with an opportunity to employ technology in ways that promote human empowerment, foster collaboration, and establish long-term bases for economic success. Additionally, it promotes human dignity and accountability to future generations (Richards, 2019). Public institution leaders are enthused about the potential of the 4IR. Public service leaders must have a comprehensive understanding of the 4IR since the public sector determines policy direction and a path for the adoption and integration of technology. This expertise will enable them to capitalise on the opportunities presented by the 4IR. Mittal (2020) argued successfully carrying out digital transformation initiatives, like AI, relies on advancements in technology, strong digital skills, and new business models. These opportunities affect not only citizens who receive services but also the daily work of public sector employees who must adapt to the 4IR and provide quality service.

Humanising Digital Transformation

A common pitfall in 4IR policy is an intense focus on efficiency, technical proficiency, and innovation without considering human sensitivity. Governments run the danger of alienating voters and eroding public trust when they put performance numbers ahead of people. Empathic public servants and their leaders can lower this risk by reviving the relational and emotional parts of governance. Governments may establish inclusive systems that reflect common values by including residents and public employees through participatory forums, listening to their concerns, and incorporating feedback into policy decisions. Through empathy-driven public engagement, citizens become active contributors to digital change rather than passive beneficiaries of e-governance. The Transformational Leadership theory, which is frequently applied in public sector organisations, serves as the foundation for this concept (Jonck, 2024:2) Moynihan, Pandey, and Wright (2014:87-104) state that the rising prominence of transformational leadership shows a move away from the self-interest focus found in the new public management model, toward values that benefit communities and public servants. The government must lead and guide the country through the 4IR as regulators and policymakers in the digital revolution.

Key Institutional Role Players for Promoting the 4IR

The important role players in the government's response to the opportunities and problems posed by the 4IR are listed in this section. The 4IR's implementation is directly impacted by these role players. Leaders and employees of these organisations must continue to be dedicated to enhancing the advantages of the 4IR. They are essential for carrying out a policy direction that is intended to effectively navigate the 4IR. Through these several entities, the public service actively facilitates the 4IR and plays a part in its promotion.

The Presidential Commission on the Fourth Industrial Revolution (PC4IR)

According to Van der Westhuizen (2021:106), the Commission was

established in 2018 as a strategic response to manage the 4IR. The Commission leads South Africa's efforts to meet the challenges posed by the 4IR. The Commission formulates and proposes policies and strategic initiatives aimed at positioning the country as a frontrunner in the development of the 4IR in the public sector (Ndabeni-Abrahams, 2018:1).

The Department of Communications and Digital Technologies (DCDT)

The government's overarching data policy is realised through the DCDT (Ntlatlapa, 2021:26-27). The department is a key player in leading the country's digital transformation agenda, which includes ensuring technological literacy and access to ICT infrastructure across all regions in the country.

State Information Technology Agency (SITA)

According to Mosehlana (2018:700), the role of the SITA is to develop digital solutions for the government to address service delivery shortcomings and is tasked with formulating a government-wide integrated e-government platform. The SITA also serves a role in cybersecurity and e-government initiatives (South African Government, 2017).

National Treasury

National Treasury allocates funding for digital infrastructure, research and innovation in South Africa's response to the 4IR (Mosehlana, 2018:701). The National Treasury assesses the economic impact of the country's 4IR initiatives and strategic response. It is important that public sector leaders ensure that financial resources allocated for the acquisition of 4IR technologies are managed effectively and in accordance with the budgets for digital transformation initiatives (Mosehlana, 2018:701).

National e-Government Executive Committee (NEEC)

The NEEC operates in support of the IDTC to coordinate and ensure that government departments are committed to the National e-Government Programme and provide strategic oversight on public concerns related to 4IR and e-government (Mosehlana, 2018:700).

Government Information Technology Officers Council (GITOC)

Mosehlana (2018:700) stated that the GITOC serves in both a technical and advisory capacity on issues relating to the digitalisation of e-government services. The deputy minister of the DPSA, Dr Chana Pilane-Majake, stated that the GITOC is an important ICT support component of government (Gabara, 2023: internet source). Furthermore, the GITOC seeks to apply innovative methods and approaches to digitalise government departments' services and promote the development of software that is owned by the government.

Legislative Frameworks for 4IR Implementation

The identification of the crucial legislative frameworks that are relevant for the implementation of the 4IR is imperative to capture the significance of the government's role as regulators of the 4IR in the country. The frameworks outlined below reflect the government's commitment to ensuring that digital transformations occur in ways that adhere to the regulatory requirements that have been set in place.

National Integrated ICT Policy White Paper (2016)

This paper includes interventions and policies that address the digital divide and ensure access to ICTs for all in the country and sets the policy direction for universal broadband access and provides a foundation for digital development across public sector services (DPSA, 2024).

According to the DPSA (2024:9), this policy identified these fundamentals to achieve a digital society:

- The modernisation of government through digital transformation seeks to achieve developmental goals while improving efficiency within the public sector. The digitalisation of services is expected to drive greater demand for internet connectivity and stimulate expansion in e-commerce and related industries;
- Digital access is concerned with enabling all citizens to meaningfully engage in the digital environment and leverage ICTs to enhance their overall well-being;
- Digital inclusion aims to guarantee that every South African can benefit from participation in the digital economy, ensuring that no one is left behind.

National Development Plan (2030)

The framework highlights emerging technologies as a central catalyst for socio-economic development and enhanced governance (Chigova, 2021:1069-1073). Gonese and Ngepah (2024:1) note that the National Development Plan 2030 underscores the potential of 4IR technologies to improve socio-economic conditions and boost public sector efficiency. However, these advancements may also result in substantial employment reduction, increased inequality, and a widening digital divide. Mngxati and de Haas (2019) further contend that the integration of 4IR could displace approximately 1.5 million jobs in South Africa by 2030, posing a significant challenge that the NDP 2030 must address.

Electronic Communications Act of 2005

Initially, this framework was established as the Telecommunications Act of 1996 to promote access to ICTs and 4IR technologies to previously disadvantaged groups during the apartheid regime (Mosehlana, 2018:696). However, it was later revised and enacted in 2005. The Act supports infrastructure development that is necessary for digital inclusion and access to 4IR technologies (Mokefe, 2023:1092).

Cyber Crimes Act of 2020

The Cybercrimes Act of 2020 is a crucial framework addressing the concerns related to cybersecurity and cybercrimes that are prevalent in the 4IR era (Snail & Musoni, 2023:1-25). The Cybercrimes Act supports the secure adoption of 4IR within the government and ensures that there are measures in place that can protect the public sector from cybercrimes (Snail & Musoni, 2023:1-25). This is because the act seeks to provide legislation that will lead to the criminalisation of offences related to cybercrimes (Snail & Musoni, 2023:1-25).

According to Nhede, Mazenda, and Masiya (5:2022), cybersecurity is one of the significant aspects of the 4IR that governments should prioritise and ensure that the public sector and citizens are not victims of cybercrimes like hacking of confidential information. Subban and Jarbandhan (2019:154) observe that continuous employee skills development initiatives in the government would be crucial to combat cybercrimes.

The Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA) of 2013

The POPIA of 2013 regulates the processing of personal data by public entities (Mokefe, 2023:1090). It represents a crucial legislation in the era of AI, and other 4IR technologies that ensures data privacy and ethical governance when processing information (Adams & Adeleke 2020:146-149). Enhancing the POPIA's involvement in public organisations that deal with individuals' personal data is crucial. According to Van der Westhuizen (2021:94), attempts to protect public digital information have been spurred by recent data breaches. According to Subban and Jarbandhan (2019), the government has to invest more in dependable and long-lasting cyber defence measures.

Digital Government Policy Framework (DGPF) of 2024

The significance of digital transformation and the necessity of forming alliances with various organisations to improve service provision are highlighted in the recently drafted Digital Government Policy Framework (DPSA, 2024). The DGPF was established to assist the government in creating frameworks that can help address the opportunities and demands presented by the 4IR. The DPSA (2024:5) claims that the present digital transformation rules are antiquated and do not encourage the advancement of digital technologies.

The aforementioned legislative frameworks demonstrate how the government regulates digital transformation in the 4IR. The South African Constitution is a crucial document that outlines the primary legal principles for governance, such as the right to equality, information access and service delivery. These ideas are critical to the 4IR's inclusion and digital development. The government's dedication to establishing regulations and upholding laws pertaining to public sector digital transformation projects is evident in regulatory frameworks.

Conclusion

The government's responsibility in advancing the 4IR goes beyond only making policy and infrastructure investments. It necessitates developing empathy as a governing concept. As previously mentioned, empathy ensures that social inclusion, emotional intelligence, and ethical responsibility are supported by the digital developments of the 4IR. The government can increase resilience, rebuild public confidence, and bridge the gap between technology advancement and human well-being by integrating empathy into leadership development, policy creation, and organisational culture. In the end, empathy turns digital transformation and governance into a human-centred process that promotes group advancement in the 4IR era. The government facilitates digital transformation, as demonstrated by the debate of its crucial institutional role in the 4IR. The government's crucial role as a regulator of digital transformation is further highlighted by defining the primary regulatory frameworks pertinent to the 4IR.

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